

ZULFIYAKHANIM IS A MIRROR OF UZBEK WOMEN IN LIFE

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ANNOTATION: this article presents scientific and theoretical views on the role model of zulfiyakhanim in the lives of Uzbek girls, women, the way in which Uzbek women lived, the definition of motherhood, the image of Zulfiyakhanim by writers, the establishment of the zulfiyakhanim prize.

Key words: female soul, loyalty, women's freedom, human beauty, dissolution, memory, mother, peace, Uzbek woman, milky way.

In his own words, Adib Rasul Gamzatov of Dagestan said: "Zulfiya is a creator united by the fate of his people. Indeed, Zulfiyakhanim describes everything in life as "a woman listening with a woman's heart, seeing through a woman's eyes, perceiving and describing with a woman's word, singing with a woman's voice." His life path, his love for his life partner Hamid Olimjan, his true Uzbek woman's loyalty, his Zulfiyakhanim, who remains a symbol of perseverance, has many qualities that will set an example for our young girls. Zulfiya Israilova was born in Tashkent in 1915. During his studies in the land of knowledge, he became acquainted with the patterns of Uzbek classical literature. The craving for Fiction also woke up at this time. Beginning in the 1930s, his first poems were printed in the collections "young cadres", "third syllable" in newspapers and magazines. As early as Zulfiya's first step into poetry, the issue of women's liberation is central. His poems from the pre-Great Patriotic War will be devoted to the creation of the image of a free Uzbek girl working in a collective farm and in factories. About 20 poems of 1932 "sheets of life" were printed. It covered

some of the most actual issues of the time, though not particularly thorough during this period. The poet does not understand women's liberation as just leaving paranji and walking down the street with an open face, but interprets it as a real liberation only when it is associated with a renewed pleasure of work. Zulfiya shows that "the beauty of man is in labor" through personal examples of "girls on par with The Sun". In the pen of the poetess after the Patriotic War, scientists, doctors, tractor women, girls driving cars, advanced growers, loving mothers find their expression. His poems "to my friend", "a day in the field", "Mother", "Voice of the Uzbek girl", "Zootechnical girl", "Shepherd", "wives who did not throw their Parangisi", "were that sunflower", "two comrades" reflect the above thought. Zulfia's poem "To My Friend" contains many of her events despite its small size. This poem is the fruit of the harmonization of our historical progress in the lyrical thoughts of the poet. The many-year historical path of Uzbek girls is given through the memories of the poet. Zulfiya creates a vivid history by incorporating the inner feelings, pity, sadness, encouragement, joys of the lyrical hero in his account of the historical events of the milky way. One after another, the Uzbek girl draws such events as her incarnation as an active builder, being a loving mother, the loss of her life partner – her husband on the roads of the Great Patriotic War, and nevertheless actively participating in the work of society.

In the image of the mother, the poet sees a person who embodies the meaning of the world-the world. The mother is an active participant and builder of all material and spiritual aspects of our society.

Mother is a shepherd, grower, scientist, weaver,
An astrologer who knows the science of the stars.
When you discuss the secret of nature,
Both the Qur'an and the Bible are silent.

In these verses, the mother further glorifies the mother by portraying her most honourable function as a mature man nurturing and nurturing, as well as standing in line in all areas of work performed by men and working hard. Another example of this is Sharaf Boshbekov's "the Iron wife", which also showed that iron cannot withstand

the perseverance of Uzbek women. In the image of Aydin in the “Aydin “ ocher of zulfiyakhanim, the types of millions of Uzbek women who had been humiliated in the past became hur during the Soviet era, which hurhayot was forgiving, harmonized.

In an era when it was of great importance to hold international meetings calling for peace to send Inter-Country representatives to strengthen peace work all over the world, the poet Zulfiya was in Colombo, Cairo as the representative of the Uzbek people on these issues. In conclusion, we can say that Zulfiyakhanim is a woman with all the noble qualities of this people as a person, while being a poet with a special place in Uzbek poetry. His life is a sign for all Uzbek women. Because his hard work in life, constant progress is devoted to the chapter of love , his tireless search for artistic creativity and his unwillingness to resonate in life’s difficulties, his lack of self-esteem in the face of his achievements, arouses admiration in the hearts of any girl or woman. People’s poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla Oripov says about our poet Zulfiyakhanim: "wonderful poet sister. Since Sister Zulfiya’s poetic talent stands in the cup of qualities, this talent is the oily sign that made the name of our poet known to the world. Sister Zulfia, in her articles in conversation, keeps humbling themselves in the idea and tells them with a beautiful nadomat that they have created little ”.Zulfiyakhanim was noted not only by writers, poets, but also by his humanity, humility in the Uzbek people. In the work of zulfiyakhanim, the fate of the Uzbek woman occupies an important place, her active role in the life of the country does not hide the fact that she was among the household chores, a woman obedient to her husband, who was both a bachelor and a ruler at home, should bow her head.

In conclusion, we can say that Zulfiyakhanim is a woman with all the noble qualities of this people as a person, while being a poet with a special place in Uzbek poetry. His life is a sign for all Uzbek women. Because his hard work in life, constant progress is devoted to the chapter of love , his tireless search for artistic creativity and his unwillingness to resonate in life’s difficulties, his lack of self-esteem in the face of his achievements, arouses admiration in the hearts of any girl or woman. On June 10, 1999, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan established the State prize named

after Zulfiyakhonim, noting the great merits of the outstanding poet in the spread of our culture. This award was established as a result of the state policy aimed at supporting the women of our country in order to deservedly Award women who are becoming an example to their peers in such fields as science, literature, education, sports, culture between the ages of 14 and 30. This will certainly serve to make every Uzbek girl creative without stopping within her science and benefit the future of our country. The life path of my zulfiyakhan is the life path of a real Soviet child for the people.

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